

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

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ABSTRACT

In Europe, around 70% of soils are currently degraded due to soil threats (STs). Global changes, such as climate change and intensive land use potentially contribute to an increase of ST on soils. In addition, STs interact and should thus be analyzed jointly for a thorough understanding of their synergies and co-occurrences. The identification and analysis of such coherent associations, often referred to as "**bundles**", is an integrated means of assessing and visualizing these interactions.

This report proposes a first assessment, at the European Union (EU) scale, of ST bundles for 2050 under land use change and two climate change scenarios corresponding to two contrasted Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5). In the framework of the SERENA project, STs are processes, the one considered as most important being soil organic carbon (SOC) loss, soil erosion, soil compaction, and soil sealing. Indicators used to assess these STs were selected based on scientific soundness, data availability, and stakeholder relevance. As a result, the change between 1980 (date of European WOSIS data measurements) and 2050 in SOC stock to the whole soil depth or to 1 m for deeper soils was chosen as indicator for SOC loss; the change in topsoil bulk density for the same dates, for soil compaction; the soil loss by water erosion in 2050, for soil erosion; the change in sealed surface between 2012 and 2050, for soil sealing. This analysis was based on available European databases that is SoilGrids for soil, LUISA for land use and WordClim for climate. To assess soil compaction and SOC loss by 2050, a Digital Soil Mapping (DSM) approach was used through QRF algorithm. For SOC loss, only the part of SOC younger than 70 years was used in this assessment. Soil erosion was quantified through the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE). Due to the absence of soil sealing projections for 2050, we combined the projection in soil artificialization for 2050 (LUISA data) with the average degree of soil sealing per NUTS3 estimated for 2012 using the European Environment Agency (2018) for each artificialized soil class (urbanization, industrial and infrastructure).

Twenty bundles were identified and grouped by interpretation into five groups: soils not projected to be under threat by 2050 (42.5% and 39.2% of the EU for SSP1-2.6 and SSP5 respectively); soils experiencing only one ST with significant intensity (34.5% and 32.2% of the EU for SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5 respectively); soils experiencing two STs with significant intensity (22.1% and 23.4% of the EU for SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5 respectively); soils experiencing three STs with significant intensity (0.9% and 5.2% of the EU for SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5 respectively). These results showed that more than two thirds of Europe will experience no STs or only one by 2050 Overall, the impact of the chosen SSPs on the bundles was rather limited and generally lower than the model precision, despite some regional marked changes at more regional scale. SSP5-8.5 scenario increasing bundles with three STs, representing an increase of 4.3% in the EU territory. The maps of ST bundles revealed that area experiencing several threats are mainly located in Baltic countries, south of Finland and Sweden, Denmark, most of England, Spain, Portugal, France, Romania, and northern part of Germany, Poland and Italy, as well as in central European countries and are mainly driven by climate change and land use. The apparent contradiction between 70% of the soils being degraded and more of two thirds of these soils not or only poorly affected by STs in 2050 is due to the fact that while STs are processes, "degraded soils" refers to a state of the soil compared to a reference.

Further steps will consist in (1) a quantitative analysis of the relationships between the spatial distribution of bundles and that of the potential bundle drivers such as climate change, land use change and soil types; (2) gathering the feedback from stakeholders on the final output of our work both at European and national scales

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

AOA	Area of Applicability
ASA	Artificialized Soil
CEC	Cation exchange capacity
CMIP	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project
CV	Coefficient of Variation
DSM	Digital Soil Mapping
ESDAC	European Soil Data Centre
EU	European Union
FAMD	Factorial Analysis for Mixed Data
GCM	Global Climate Model
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
LUISA	Land Use-based Integrated Sustainability Assessment
LULC	Land Use Land Cover
MCA	Multivariate Correspondence Analysis
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
OOB	Out-Of-Bag
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PICP	Prediction Interval Coverage Probability
QRF	Quantile Regression Forest
R ²	Coefficient of Determination
RDA	Redundancy Analysis
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathways
RFE	Recursive Feature Elimination
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
RUSLE	Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation
SSA	Soil Sealing Area
SD	Standard Deviation
SOC	Soil Organic Carbon
SSP	Shared Socio-economic Pathways
ST	Soil Threat
WoSIS	World Soil Information Service
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

Around 70% of Europe's soils are degraded, due to the soil threats (STs) caused by the intensive land use and the effects of climate change (European Commission, 2020). The STs are processes that can degrade soil functions and the ecosystem services provided by soil (EJP SOIL glossary, 2022), affecting plant support, reducing the quality of the soil's physical, chemical and biological properties. On a global scale, the main STs include soil erosion, compaction, loss of SOC, nutrient imbalance, salinization, soil sealing, loss of biodiversity, contamination, acidification and waterlogging (Caon and Vargas, 2017).

The STs evaluated in this SERENA deliverable were selected through a prioritization assessment of the most important STs by each SERENA partner considering end-user's requirements, project Member States (MS) requirements and EU expectations. The most important STs identified are SOC loss, soil erosion, soil compaction, and soil sealing (Antón et al., 2022; Montagne et al., 2023). Among these STs, soil compaction, soil erosion and SOC loss result from the action of human activities on soil processes and are therefore interconnected. SOC loss is considered as the most critical in Europe given the importance of SOC as a source of nutrients for plants and for supporting the soil physical, chemical and biological properties (Yigini and Panagos, 2016). It results from the intensive use of the soil, non-adoption of good management practices and climate variability that causes SOC loss, as CO₂ to the atmosphere by SOC decomposition. Soil erosion is also responsible for SOC loss. In turn, SOC loss induces soil degradation that affects soil health, soil functioning and consequently reduces the supply of soil ecosystem services (Lal, 2003; Meena et al., 2022; Steinhoff-Knopp et al., 2021; Tian et al., 2016). In addition, climatic factors such as precipitation and temperature are key drivers at global and regional scales, affecting carbon inputs into the soil and SOC decomposition (Wiesmeier et al., 2019). In turns, soil erosion that induces soil losses under the action of water, wind, tillage and harvest is one of the main STs in the EU (European Commission, 2006), which depends on several factors, such as land use, slope, conservation practices, rainfall and soil erodibility (Coblinski et al., 2019; Englund et al., 2020; Panagos et al., 2015d). Soil compaction, that results in an increase of soil bulk density and a decrease of soil porosity, mostly occurs due to intensive use of agricultural machinery (Abu-Hamdeh, 2003; Archer and Smith, 1972). The increase in soil bulk density directly reduces the root growth, soil aeration, water infiltration, the capacity of the soil to store water and SOC, increasing surface water runoff, contributing then to the soil erosion (Lamandé et al., 2018; Stolte et al., 2015).

As mentioned above, the selected STs are interacting. Since, as already discussed, SOC impacts the soil structure, a low SOC content may result in a low structural quality of the soil, reducing the stability of the aggregates and facilitating their transport by water erosion (Bauer, 1974; Gliński et al., 2011; Guerra, 1994), but also may reduce soil porosity and increase soil bulk density, increasing the risk of soil compaction (Indoria et al., 2020) as soil compaction is sensitive to even small changes in the amount of SOC (Soane, 1990). However, the inverse relationship also exists. A compacted soil restricts root growth (Nawaz et al., 2013) preventing the addition of organic matter to the soil (Brevik, 2013) and directly influence soil erosion by increasing the surface runoff of the water that cannot infiltrate the compacted layer, thereby increasing the particle detachment and therefore soil erosion (Nawaz et al., 2013). Soil erosion, by removing the upper layer of the soil, the richest in SOC, strongly affects the amount of SOC in the eroded soil that is redistributed in the watershed (Doetterl et al., 2016; Świtoniak et al., 2016; Thaler et al., 2021).

The last considered ST, soil sealing results from the covering of the soils by artificial material such as, asphalt, concrete from buildings, constructions, roads, industrial and various types of urban structures (Ginzky et al., 2019). As the most intensive form of land takes, sealed soils result in the loss of most of their functions and ecosystem services (Munafò et al., 2013), with almost irreversible effects. Since soil sealing affects all the soil functions, it also acts on the expression of the other soil threats even if these interactions are less clearly quantified in the literature to the best of our knowledge.

Due to the interconnected nature of STs and their collective impact on soil health, they should be analyzed jointly for a thorough understanding of their synergies and co-occurrences. The identification and analysis of such coherent associations, often referred to as "**bundles**", has been already developed within the framework of the study of ecosystem services as an integrated means of assessing and visualizing interactions. Here we aim to extend the bundles approach to soil threats, something that as far as we are aware has not been done in the literature. The rationale is that such an approach can potentially provide insights on underlying common drivers of soil degradation. In this way, STs bundles are defined as a 'set of soil threats', that appear together repeatedly in time or space (adapted, after Potschin-Young et al., 2018). In a recent review, Saidi and Spray (2018) distinguished two main strategies from the literature that accounted for more than 90% of papers reviewed: cluster analyses (k-means or hierarchical) and graphical/tabular detection using lower dimensional projections with principal component analysis (PCA), factor analysis, multiple correspondence analysis (MCA) or multidimensional scaling. Moreover, several methodologies exist in the literature to evaluate the associations of STs, such as: correlation analysis and bagplots (Jopke et al., 2015), which evaluate the interaction of two STs; overlap analysis (Egoh et al., 2009, 2008); PCA (Maes et al., 2012); MCA (Richards et al., 2020); Factorial Analysis for Mixed data (FAMD) (Mouchet et al., 2014); and cluster analysis, such as K-means or Gaussian mixed models (Mouchet et al., 2014; Raudsepp-Hearne et al., 2010).

Finally, global changes, such as climate change and intensive land use, will affect the actions of STs, potentially intensifying their effects on the soil. According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), global temperatures are expected to increase by between 1 and 2°C by 2050 with a change in global precipitation patterns, leading to more severe drought events (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2023). This change in climate threatened food security through its effects on soil processes (Brevik, 2013). On the other hand, we will have to face a growing demand for food and raw materials leading in combination with climate change to changes in land use that will affect soils.

Therefore, projecting STs at the European scale in the future (2050) for different scenarios is of key importance for informed decision-making by the EU within the framework of its soil policy to achieve the objectives of the European Green Deal (EC-European Commission, 2019). Some projections exist in the literature for SOC loss (Yigini and Panagos, 2016) and erosion (Panagos et al., 2021). However, as mentioned above, since STs are interconnected, these evaluations should be done by a jointed evaluation of the selected STs to detect bundles at EU scale which implies to use the same input data. This is the objective of this report is to present (1) the assessment of soil threats by 2050 under the effects of land use and climate changes at the EU scale and (2) the first projection of ST bundles at a continental level. To do so, we developed a top-down mapping approach based on the European datasets and mainly on digital soil mapping (DSM) technics (**Error! Reference source not found.**). Clustering method by k-means was used to identify the ST bundles. This clustering method was chosen for its simplicity, efficiency and speed of use with large-scale datasets.

Considering the global change scenarios, we chose the climatic projections among the five emissions scenarios defined by the IPCC (in replacement of the Representative Concentration Pathways scenarios) and driven by various socioeconomic assumptions, the so-called Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs). We considered the two extreme ones: SSP1-2.6, envisioning a sustainable, low-emission pathway with stringent mitigation measures, and SSP5-8.5, representing a high-emission scenario driven by continued fossil fuel use and limited mitigation efforts with severe climate impacts (Eyring et al., 2016; O'Neill et al., 2017; Riahi et al., 2017), from two downscaled global climate models (ACCESS-CM2 and HadGEM3-GC3-LL (Dix et al., 2019; Good, 2019)). We also considered the land use change projected for 2050 by the Land Use-based Integrated Sustainability Assessment (LUIA) model. (Joint Research Centre, 2015).

Figure 1. Overall modelling framework for the mapping of the bundles of STs by 2050 based on a comprehensive assessment of four soil threats

The report is divided into 2 parts: the assessment of the spatial distribution of the 4 selected individual STs under global change and the detection and mapping of the ST bundles by 2050 (Figure 1).

2. Assessment of soil threats: Conceptual reflexion and indicators

2.1. Material and methods

In this section, we first discuss the indicators chosen for the different STs, then the methods used to assess them followed by the sources of data used and finally the way the data is presented.

2.1.1. Soil threat definitions and indicators choice

STs are assessed by indicators. However, for a given ST, numerous indicators exist in the literature (Montagne et al., 2023). SERENA task 2.3 evaluated, for each ST, the scientific soundness of these indicators based on various criteria and defined “ideal” indicators (those with a higher level of scientific soundness to fit the STs in question) and “realistic” indicators (those which are generally used in current available information) (D2.3.1 in section 4.2; Montagne et al., 2023). Based on their analysis, for each of the considered ST, we selected either the ideal indicator when feasible, or by default the realistic one to be assessed at the European scale (Table 1). To be noted, in the case of soil erosion, the choice of a realistic indicator, modifies the definition of this ST, limiting it to the soil erosion by water and neglecting soil erosion by wind, tillage and harvest. For soil sealing, as there are no soil sealing projections for the future, soil artificialization area was used instead of soil sealing area. We are aware that all the artificialized soils are not necessarily sealed, as gardens for example are included in artificialized soils but are not sealed. We thus estimated the overestimation of this threat made by using the artificialized area instead of the sealed area (see section 2.2.4.). For SOC loss, some estimations exist for 2050 (Yigini and Panagos, 2016) for the topsoil but not for the whole soil depth.

Table 1. List of indicators ("ideal" or "realistic") used for the different soil threats selected for a harmonization of assessment of soil threats at the European scale (based on SERENA T2.3)

Soil threats	Type	Indicator	Short definition
SOC loss	Ideal	Change in SOC stocks (kC ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	Change over time in soil organic carbon stocks over the whole soil depth
Soil erosion	Realistic	Soil loss by water erosion (t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	Yearly soil losses by water erosion
Soil compaction	Ideal	Change in topsoil bulk density (kg m ⁻³ yr ⁻¹)	Change over time in topsoil bulk density
Soil sealing	Realistic	Degree of soil sealing change (%)	Change in the proportion of an area that is covered by artificial, (semi)impermeable materials

2.1.2. Soil threats indicators assessment and projection

Figure 1 summarizes the approach chosen to evaluate the individual STs at the European scale and the interactions considered among soil threats (changes in SOC contents for assessments of erosion by 2050 or bulk density change). We decided to perform the evaluation of the individual STs at a resolution of 1km.

2.1.2.1. For soil compaction, assessment of the bulk density changes in topsoil

2.1.2.1.1. DSM estimation of the bulk density by 2050

Changes in bulk density in topsoil (0-30 cm), the chosen indicator for soil compaction, was calculated as the difference in bulk density in the topsoil between 1980 (date of soil profiles sampling of most site from ISRIC's World Soil Information Service (WoSIS)) and 2050. While European soil databases of soil bulk density in topsoil exist in the literature for 1980 (e.g. SoilGrids, Poggio et al., 2021), no topsoil bulk density estimation was available in the literature for 2050 to the best of our knowledge. To project bulk density to 2050, we applied a DSM approach (Grunwald et al., 2011; McBratney et al., 2003; Minasny and McBratney, 2016) based on the Quantile Regression Forest (QRF) algorithm that was built up on the current map in a first step. In a second step, the covariates supposed to evolve from present to 2050 (mainly climate and land use,

) were replaced in the model for the 2050 projection. For land use, the proportion of each class was used as a covariate (including the different proportions of sealed areas). This method, also known as space-for-time substitution (Blois et al., 2013), has been already used to create maps of SOC at regional (Li et al., 2021) and national (Adhikari et al., 2014; Kuang et al., 2022) scale.

We used the QRF, that is an extension of RF that provides non-parametric estimates (Meinshausen, 2006; Meinshausen and Schiesser, 2015), in the R package *ranger* (Wright and Ziegler, 2017). For each time, four different values were computed to characterize the distribution of BD: median (0.50 quantile, $q_{0.50}$), mean, 0.05 quantile ($q_{0.05}$) and 0.95 quantile ($q_{0.95}$), i.e. the lower and upper limits of a 90% prediction interval (PI). PI indicates a range in which the true value is expected to be found, given the assigned probability. This uncertainty interval is as described in the GlobalSoilMap specifications (Arrouays et al., 2014). To calibrate the prediction model, we extracted values of bulk density and covariates on a systematic sampling grid of 40,000 pixels. The model was tuned by a 15-folds cross-validation and two repetition procedures, applied to multiple combinations of hyper-parameters (*n*tree and *m*try). The *n*tree number was finally set at 200, as already reported by Poggio et al. (2021), a number above 200 only provides an increase in metrics lower than 0.1% but requires more memory and computation time. Within the different *m*try numbers tested, *m*try values were set to half of the total number of covariates.

The DSM approach was optimized selecting the key covariates that were not strongly correlated (Spearman correlation coefficient lower than 0.9 and Principal Component Analysis (PCA)). Then Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) was employed to select the most important covariates (Xu et al., 2019). Removing unnecessary features can reduce the computational expense and time consumption and generate more robust models. We used the RFE algorithm implemented in the *caret* package (Kuhn, 2008) in the R software (R Core Team, 2020). RFE starts by fitting the model using all covariates, evaluating its performance and ranking the importance, then the less important covariates are removed. The selection of the best covariate subset was based on out-of-bag (OOB) cross-validation with 10-folds and 2 repeats and accuracy metrics, as R^2 and RMSE.

For computational reasons, we downscaled the original resolution of the different covariates to 1000m. Therefore, we computed the mean of the different continuous covariates per 1km pixels. For the land use, we computed for each class the percentage of the surface within the pixels.

Finally, for the indicator of the soil compaction, the relative changes between 1980 and the projection for 2050, was calculated using equation 1:

$$\text{SoilCompaction (\%)} = \frac{\text{BulkDensity}_{2050} - \text{BulkDensity}_{1980}}{\text{BulkDensity}_{1980}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

2.1.2.1.2. Evaluation of the DSM projection model for bulk density by 2050

The evaluation of the DSM projection model for bulk density by 2050 was done in two steps: the assessment on the model performance to predict the 1980 bulk density values by repeated cross validation and its domain of applicability by 2050.

A cross-validation is an iterative process where the dataset is divided into 15 disjunctive folds. Each fold acts as a validation set in turns to evaluate the predictions obtained from a model calibrated on the remaining 14-folds are used. This helps to comprehensively evaluate the model's performance on different subsets of the data. To enhance the reliability of the cross-validation process, the 15-folds cross-validation procedure was repeated two times. Each repetition represents an independent run of the 15-folds cross-validation. For each repetition, the dataset is randomly shuffled, and the 15-folds are created again. The metrics of the two replications were averaged.

Two parameters of accuracy were computed during the cross-validation step: the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE). The R^2 ranges from 0 to 1, with 1 being the optimal value, that is, the coefficient of determination explains the variance of models. The RMSE has the same data units as the analyzed attributes parameter and measures the model's accuracy. The closer the RMSE is to zero, the more accurate the model.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - \bar{y})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (2)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2} \quad (3)$$

Where \hat{y} is the predicted values over the test set, \bar{y} is the average of the observed values, y is the observed value, n is the number of samples with i equal to 1, 2, ... n .

Furthermore, we evaluated the estimation of the prediction uncertainty using the prediction interval coverage probability (PICP) (Shrestha and Solomatine, 2006). The PICP evaluates if the probability assigned to the PI is equal to the frequency of empirical test data within the PI. In this work, we assessed the PI at 90% which corresponds to the proportion of the test dataset that fallen within the 0.05 and 0.95 quantiles. A desirable scenario is when the PICP approaches 90%, signifying reliable assessment of uncertainty. If the PICP significantly surpasses 90%, it indicates there is a deviation between the empirical values and theoretical one which means an overestimation of uncertainty. Conversely, if the PICP is substantially lower than 90%, it suggests an underestimation of uncertainty (Poggio et al., 2021; Takoutsing and Heuvelink, 2022).

To evaluate the reliability of the model for the bulk density projection to 2050, we determined its domain of applicability for 2050, or the Area of Applicability (AOA), that represents where the model can be confidently applied based on the similarity of the distributions of the environmental properties (2050) in that area to those present in the training data (current data). If the projection to 2050 significantly differs from those seen in the training data, the model's predictions may become less reliable or even inaccurate. The resulting AOA map provides a visual representation of the regions where the model predictions can be considered reliable. For more details on the methodology see Meyer and Pebesma (2021).

2.1.2.2. For SOC loss, assessment of the SOC stock change over 1-metre depth

To assess the SOC stock changes over the whole soil depth or at a 1-metre depth for deeper soils, the chosen indicator of the SOC loss, the SOC stock in soil to 1 m at two different dates is needed. While SOC stocks assessments for different soil layers exist in the literature for 1980 at the European scale (Poggio et al., 2021, based data from soil profiles sampled in the 1980's for most of them by ISRIC's World Soil Information Service (WoSIS), Batjes et al., 2019), no SOC stocks evaluations at 1 m depth exist in the literature for 2050.

To compute SOC stock over the whole soil depth or at 1 metre for deeper soils, we summed up the stocks estimated for different layers by SoilGrids to the soil depth. For each layer, we compute the proportion of the predicted SOC stock in the layer based on whether the depth falls within the depth of the layer.

SOC stocks for 2050 were assessed by DSM as for bulk density. However, as over a time range of 70 years (1980 -2050), only a part of the SOC is likely to evolve. We therefore applied the DSM approach to the only SOC part likely to evolve. This part was estimated applying the proportion estimated by Balesdent et al. (2018) for the different soil depths. Final (2050) SOC stock was then calculated adding the fraction of SOC likely to evolve over 70 years estimated by DSM, to the fraction of SOC not likely to evolve, estimated for each soil on the 1980's data.

We used the same equation to calculate the SOC stock change and the same method to validate the obtained map as those previously described for bulk density (sections 2.1.2.1.1 and 2.1.2.1.2).

2.1.2.3. Sheet and rill erosion by water assessed by the revised universal soil loss equation

Panagos et al. (2021) proposed a soil erosion loss assessment at EU scale for 2050 using a modified version of the RUSLE approach. However, they used RCP scenarios and not the SSP ones. Furthermore, they assumed pedological conditions statics through time including SOC, and also, they used rainfall data on rainfall intensity that are not projected in the future in the current climate scenarios. We therefore performed a new erosion assessment.

The revised universal soil loss equation (RUSLE) (Renard et al., 1997) is classically used in the literature to evaluate the mean annual rates of soil loss caused by sheet and rill erosion (excluding gully erosion) at the EU scale, equation 4:

$$A = R \times K \times LS \times C \times P \quad (4)$$

where: A is the annual average soil loss ($t \text{ ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$); R, the rainfall erosivity factor ($\text{MJ mm ha}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$); K, the soil erodibility factor ($t \cdot \text{ha}^2 \cdot \text{h} \cdot \text{ha}^{-2} \cdot \text{MJ}^{-1} \cdot \text{mm}^{-1}$); LS, the slope length and steepness factor (dimensionless); C, the cover-management factor (dimensionless), and P, the conservation practices factor (dimensionless). The signification and the estimation of these different parameters is explained below.

The rainfall erosivity (R factor) represents the effect of the rainfall on soil erosion. As historical series of monthly precipitation are available at the European scale, we estimated the R-factor by equation of Wischmeier and Smith (1978), equation 5:

$$R = \sum_{m=1}^{12} 1.735 * 10^{(1.5 * \log(\frac{Pm^2}{Pa}) - 0.08188)} \quad (5)$$

where: Pm is the monthly rainfall (mm) of month m; Pa, the total annual rainfall (mm); R, the rainfall erosivity factor ($\text{MJ cm ha}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$).

To project the R factor by 2050, we averaged the precipitations produced by the ACCESS-CM2 and HadGEM3-GC31-LL global climate models for the two chosen SSP1.2-6 and SSP5.8-5 CC scenarios (Fick and Hijmans, 2017).

The soil erodibility (K factor) represents the vulnerability of the soil to detachment and transport induced by raindrops and surface runoff (LaI, 2001). Soil erodibility is a function of SOC, soil texture and soil particle size as shown in equation 6 developed by Sharpley and Williams (1990) and used for calculation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 K = & \left\{ 0.2 + 0.3 \exp \left[-0.0256 \text{Sand} \left(1 - \frac{\text{Silt}}{100} \right) \right] \right\} \\
 & * \left(\frac{\text{Silt}}{\text{Clay} + \text{Silt}} \right)^{0.3} * \left[1.0 - \frac{0.25 \text{SOC}}{\text{SOC} + \exp(3.72 - 2.95 \text{SOC})} \right], \\
 & * \left[1.0 - \frac{0.7 \text{SN}}{\text{SN} + \exp(-5.51 + 22.9 \text{SN})} \right] * 0.1317
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Where: Sand, Silt, Clay and SOC are in percent and $\text{SN} = 1 - \text{Sand}/100$. K factor with units of $\text{t ha}^2 \text{ h ha}^{-2} \text{ MJ}^{-1} \cdot \text{mm}^{-1}$.

To project the K factor by 2050, the SOC content by 2050 was projected under LULC and climate scenarios (SSP1.2-6 and SSP5.8-5) as described in section 2.1.2.2. Sand, silt and clay contents were considered as constant over time and taken from SoilGrids.

The cover-management factor (C factor) represents the impact of the different land uses on the soil losses (Panagos et al., 2015b; Renard et al., 1997). It varies from 0.01 to 1 with the 1 representing bare soil and 0.01 a land cover that provides 99% reduction in soil loss. The C factor in 2050 was estimated using the LULC product from LUISA (Joint Research Centre, 2015) for 2050 and the C-factor reference values from Panagos et al. (2015b). The original LULC product has a resolution of 100 m resolution, the proportion of each land use, and its associated C factor, within the 1 km pixel was considered. We also considered the contribution of the unsealed artificialized area in the final evaluation. The C-factor value for these areas is the average of all other C-factors that can contribute in these areas. The different C-factors are listed in the Table 2.

Table 2. Mean C-factor for the land uses classes based on Panagos et al. (2015b).

Land use	C-factor
Arable crops	0.2336
Mixed Crop Livestock	0.1646
Livestock Production	0.0903
Forests Mature	0.0011
Transitional woodland shrub	0.0219
Vineyards	0.3527
Fruit trees and berry plantations	0.2188
Olive groves	0.2273
Moors and heathland	0.05215
Sclerophyllous vegetation	0.05215
Natural Grassland	0.0435
Rice Production	0.15
Sparsely vegetated areas	0.2652
Urban unsealed	0.14
Industrial unsealed	0.14
Infrastructure unsealed	0.14
Urban green leisure unsealed	0.14

Slope length and steepness (LS factor) describes the effect of topography on soil erosion. We used the LS factors provided by Panagos et al. (2015a) at a 25 m resolution.

The conservation practices (P factor) represent the agricultural practices that reduce the mean annual rate of soil loss, such as contour farming, strip cropping, terraces and subsurface drainage. The P-factor proposed by Panagos et al. (2015c) for Europe was used.

To account for the varying contributions of different land use types that could exist in a 1km size pixel, we implemented a weighted soil erosion rate considering the proportion of each land use class within the pixel, equation 7:

$$\text{Weighted soil erosion} = \sum_i (A_i \times p_i) \quad (7)$$

where: A_i is the the annual average soil loss ($\text{t ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) (equation 4) for land use class i within a pixel; p_i , the proportion of land occupied by land use class i within the pixel (where $\sum_i p_i = 1$).

Finally, we conducted a sensitivity analysis to assess the individual impacts of RUSLE factors on soil erosion projections for 2050. C-factor values were based on the dominant land use class within the pixel. To ensure comparability and mitigate the influence of differing scales among factors, we employed a standardization procedure for each factor based on their respective mean and standard deviation. The soil erosion was then calculated by integrating these standardized factors, and a perturbation-based sensitivity analysis, one at a time (OAT), was conducted (Pianosi et al., 2016). For each factor, we defined a perturbation range from 90% to 110% of the baseline value, with increments of 1%. This range was chosen to encompass realistic fluctuations in factor values. By exploring variations within this range, we aimed to capture the potential impact of factors being slightly lower or higher than their typical values (Saltelli et al., 2007).

To validate the produced water soil erosion map at the EU scale, we compared it to the map produced by Cerdan et al. (2010), based on direct field measured water soil erosion rates from a large database from medium-sized plots in Europe. The data originates from 81 experimental sites in 19 countries, covering 2,741 plots in total, with monitoring times longer than 12 months.

2.1.2.4. For soil sealing, assessment of the change in the degree of soil sealing

While soil sealing area estimation exists for present, no soil sealing projections exist for 2050 to the best of our knowledge. The only available data are for soil artificialization estimated by projection of land uses scenarios. By soil artificialization we understand areas covered by urbanization (including medium density urban fabric, low density urban fabric and isolated or very low-density urban fabric but excluding green urban areas), industrial (including both industrial and commercial units) and infrastructure (including road and rail networks and associated land, major stations, port areas, airport areas, airport terminals and construction sites), that thus have different degree of soil sealing.

We estimated for each of these land use classes the average degree of soil sealing at NUTS level 3 based on the European Environment Agency (2018) database. This average degree of sealing was thus used to estimate for each pixel the degree of soil sealing for 2012 and 2050. At last, the relative changes between 2012 and the projection for 2050 were calculated.

2.1.3. Data sources

Since several ST indicators need soil parameters (change in SOC or bulk density and erosion), climate data (same indicators) or land use (change in SOC or bulk density and soil artificialization), the use of different data bases as input data could induce discrepancies that might arise from the diverse sources' inherent variations. To avoid this drawback, we chose a unique soil database per data type, that is SoilGrids for soil data, WorldClim for climate, and LUISA for land use (Figure 1). Data sources used to assess SOC stock change, soil bulk density change and erosion by 2050 are synthetized in tables Table 3 to Table 4.

All the raster where resample to a 1 km resolution. For land use, we computed the percentage of each land use type.

Table 3. Environmental-based covariates used in the predictive model using DSM approach for the assessment of soil compaction and SOC loss.

SCORPAN variables	Covariates	Unit	Spatial raw resolution	Source	
Soil	Bulk density	kg/dm ³	250 m	SoilGrids data.isric.org/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/home	
	Clay	%	250 m		
	Sand	%	250 m		
	Silt	%	250 m		
	Cation exchange capacity	cmol(c)/kg	250 m		
	Coarse fragments	%	250 m		
	Organic carbon density	kg/m ³	250 m		
	pH	pH	250 m		
	Soil depth	m	1 km		ESDAC
	Soil water content 33 Kpa	Kpa	250 m		OpenGeoHub zenodo.org/record/2784001#_YxCkbXZByCh
Topography	Aspect	no unit	25 m	Copernicus land.copernicus.eu/imagery-in-situ/eu-dem/eu-dem-v1.1/view	
	Elevation	m	25 m		
	Slope	%	25 m		
Climate	Bioclimatic variables*	-	1 km	See table 4	
Land use	Land use classes	no unit		See table 4	

Table 4. Input data for the assessment of the individual RUSLE factors

RUSLE factors	Input data	Unit	Spatial raw resolution	Source
P factor Support practices	P factor	-	100 m	ESDAC esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/themes/support-practices-factor
LS factor Slop length and steepness	LS factor	-	100 m	ESDAC esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/ls-factor-slope-length-and-steepness-factor-eu
C factor Cover management	Land use	No unit	100 m	LUISA joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/luisa_en
R factor Rainfall erosivity	Annual precipitation Monthly precipitation	mm mm	1 km 1 km	WorldClim www.worldclim.org/
K factor Soil erodibility	Clay Sand Silt Soil organic carbon content	% % % g/kg	250 m 250 m 250 m 250 m	SoilGrids data.isric.org/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/home

Table 5. List of variables used to represent climate and land use changes scenarios used to assess soil compaction, SOC loss and soil erosion, and the respective source. Climate data used for 2050 were the mean of the results produced by the two ACCESS-CM2 and HadGEM3-GC31-LL global climate models for the two selected SSPs

Parameters	Variables	Unit	Raw resolution	Database	Period
Precipitation	Monthly total precipitation	mm			
Bioclimatic variables	Annual mean temperature	°C		<i>worldclim.org</i> (Dix et al., 2019; Good, 2019)	Historical (1970-2000) to 2050 (SSP 1.2-6 and SSP 5.8-5)
	Mean Diurnal Range	°C			
	Isothermality	No unit			
	Temperature Seasonality	°C			
	Max Temperature of Warmest Month	°C			
	Min Temperature of Coldest Month	°C			
	Temperature Annual Range	°C			
	Mean Temperature of Wettest Quarter	°C			
	Mean Temperature of Driest Quarter	°C			
	Mean Temperature of Warmest Quarter	°C	1 km		
	Mean Temperature of Coldest Quarter	°C			
	Annual Precipitation	mm			
	Precipitation of Wettest Month	mm			
	Precipitation of Driest Month	mm			
	Precipitation Seasonality	Fraction			
	Precipitation of Wettest Quarter	mm			
	Precipitation of Driest Quarter	mm			
	Precipitation of Warmest Quarter	mm			
Precipitation of Coldest Quarter	mm				
Land use	Land use classes	No unit	100 m	<i>LUISA - joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/luisa_en</i> (Joint Research Centre, 2017)	2012 to 2050

2.1.4. Definition of classes of soil threats intensities

The last step in the evaluation of STs was their classification into intensity classes (thresholding). For the soil erosion classes, we used erosion used in the literature and chosen for the soil erosion cookbook by SERENA WP2:

- 0-1 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ : negligible soil loss;
- 1-2 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹: very slight soil loss;
- 2-5 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹: slight soil loss;
- 5-10 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹: moderate soil loss;
- > 10 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹: severe soil loss.

For soil sealing, the intensity classes are as follows: more than -80% (de-sealing), from -80% to 30% (non-significant change); more than 30% (significant increase in soil sealing). The class limits were based on Smith et al. (2019). To be note that de-sealing of soils (> -80 %) are only encountered for few pixels.

For SOC loss and soil compaction, there are no intensity classes established in the literature for the chosen indicators that is respectively SOC stock to one-metre change and topsoil bulk density change. However, due to the complexity of the evaluation of the indicators and to the inherent uncertainties associated, we do not consider changes lower than $\pm 10\%$ as significant. For the soil compaction and SOC loss, we considered four classes:

- from -40% to -10 %;
- from -10 % to 10% (non-significant change);
- from 10% to 40% and
- > 40%.

2.2. Threats to soil on EU territory by 2050

2.2.1. Projection of soil compaction by 2050

2.2.1.1. *DSM predictive model for soil bulk density: importance of variables and validation*

The most important variable used for predicting the 1980 bulk densities (SoilGrids data) was SOC content (Figure 2), which is logical as SOC is used in pedotransfer function to predict soil bulk density in SoilGrids (Poggio et al., 2021). Other important variables are related to climate, slope and elevation. Surprisingly, soil particle size distribution also considered in the pedotransfer function used to predict bulk density doesn't rank very high, nor does land use. When predicting bulk density for 2050, the main effect expected will thus be due to the change in SOC content and climate but not in land use.

Figure 2. Importance of covariates used in the QRF model for predicting soil bulk density for 1980

Table 6 shows the cross-validation performance data obtained on the bulk density data from SoilGrids. The cross validation yielded R^2 of 0.96 and RMSE of 0.04, that is an excellent prediction capacity of the bulk density DSM model to reproduce the SoilGrids predictions. Regarding the uncertainty on assessment (PICP for 90% PI), we obtained a value of 95.19, meaning that there is a difference of about 5% between the theoretical (90%) and the empirical one (95.19) which we considered a small deviation. We then assume a reliable assessment of the uncertainty.

Table 6. Cross-validation performances of the prediction model for bulk density applying QRF algorithm

Indicator	Unit	Cross-Validation		Uncertainty
		R^2	RMSE	PICP90
Bulk density	g/cm ³	0.96	0.04	95.19

For the 2050 projection, we determined the area of applicability (AOA) of the model (Figure 3a,b). For the two SSPs, the model remains in its applicability domain (pixels in green color) for most EU in 2050, except in small areas in northeastern Italy and southwestern Slovenia. We can thus consider the results of bulk density prediction for 2050 as reliable.

QRF validity domain for bulk density by 2050

Figure 3. Area of applicability (AOA) analysis for bulk density in 2050 considering land use and climate change under SSP1-2.6 (a) and SSP5-8.5 (b)

2.2.1.2. *Effect of scenarios for 2050 on soil compaction estimated by a change in bulk density between 1980 and 2050*

In 2050, the mean bulk density of EU soils will not significantly have evolved compared to 1980 whatever the scenario considered (Table 7). Nevertheless, 4.20% and 5.98% of the EU soils will have experienced a high increase in bulk density and 17.65% and 19.26% a moderate one under SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5 scenario, respectively. These increases will mainly occur in northern and eastern Europe, with the highest intensities of soil compaction in Latvia, Estonia, southern Finland and southern Sweden (Figure 4). These important changes are partially linked to the change in soil organic carbon projected in the same areas (see section 2.2.2).

Table 7. Descriptive statistics of change (%) between 1980 and 2050 in soil bulk density under different climate change scenarios (SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5) by 2050

	Unit	SPP	Mean	Median	CV	SD
Soil compaction	%	1-2.6	7.51	3.25	1.85	13.86
		5-8.5	9.14	3.91	1.77	16.16

Figure 4. Soil compaction by 2050: classes of soil bulk density change between 1980 and 2050 considering land use and climate change under SSP1-2.6 (a) and SSP5-8.5 (b)

The difference between the two scenarios on the bulk density changes between 1980 and 2050 is not significant when the whole EU is considered (Table 7 and Figure 5a and b). Nevertheless, in some regions (northern and eastern/central Europe, as well as in the UK), a more pronounced bulk density increase (at least 10% higher) is observed for the SSP 5-8.5 compared to the SSP1-2.6 (Figure 5c).

Figure 5. Relative changes (%) in soil bulk densities between 1980 and 2050 under land use and climate change for two contrasted climatic scenarios: SSP1-2.6 (a) and SSP 5-8.5 (b). Areas with bulk density increase at least 10% higher (the orange dotted lines on the histograms) for SSP 5-8.5 than for SSP1-2.6, in orange on the map, (c)

2.2.2. Projection of SOC stock loss at 1-metre between 1980 and 2050

2.2.2.1. DSM predictive model for SOC stock: importance of variables and validation

The most important covariates used by the QRF model in the construction of the SOC stock QRF prediction model are related to climate (temperature - maximum temperature of the warmest month, annual mean temperature, minimum temperature of the coldest month, mean diurnal range, mean temperature of the wettest quarter - and precipitation - warmest quarter precipitation, annual precipitation), some land use classes (croplands, wetlands, forests and pasture), elevation that can be a proxy of climate, and CEC (Figure 6). Climate and land use covariates are expected, as it is well known that the dynamic of SOC depends on these factors. Soil depth is also rather important in the model. It clearly plays a fundamental role in the amount of SOC stock.

Figure 6. Importance of covariates used in the QRF model for predicting SOC stock to 1-metre depth in 1980

Table 8 shows the cross-validation performance obtained on the SOC stock over the whole soil depth or to 1-metre for deeper soils from SoilGrids (Poggio et al., 2021). The cross-validation of the model showed excellent performance, with an R^2 of 0.86 with 16.23 of RMSE. The model is able to reproduce a large part of the variability of the SoilGrids predictions. Regarding the uncertainty on the SOC stock to 1-metre prediction, we obtained a PICP value of 93.36, signifying reliable assessment of uncertainties.

Table 8. Cross-validation performances of prediction model for SOC stock applying QRF algorithm

Indicator	Unit	Cross-Validation		Uncertainty
		R^2	RMSE	PICP90
SOC stock to 1m	t ha ⁻¹	0.86	16.23	93.36

For the projections for 2050, we determined the AOA of the model (Figure 7a,b). For the two SSPs, as for the change in bulk density, the model remains in its applicability domain (green color) for most EU in 2050, except in small areas in the extreme northern part of Italy and part of Austria (red color). It is to be noted that the area where the model cannot be applied is a bit larger than for the bulk density estimation. Nevertheless, we can consider the results of SOC stock at 1m depth predictions for 2050 as reliable over most EU.

QRF validity domain for SOC stock by 2050

Figure 7. Area of applicability (AOA) analysis for SOC stock in 2050 considering land use and climate change under SSP1-2.6 (a) and SSP5-8.5 (b)

2.2.2.2. Effect of scenarios on the loss between 1980 and 2050 in SOC stock over 1-metre depth

Figure 8. SOC loss: Classes of SOC stock loss over the whole soil profile or over 1m when the soil is deeper, between 1980 and 2050, considering land use and two climatic scenarios: SSP1-2.6 (a) and SSP5-8.5 (b).

In 2050, the mean SOC stock over the whole soil depth or at 1 m when the soil is deeper for the EU soils will not significantly have changed compared to 1980 whatever the scenario considered (Table 9). Nevertheless, 25.6% and 31.3% of the EU soils will experience SOC loss between 1980 and 2050 for SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5 respectively. These SOC stock losses will mainly occur in northern Europe, eastern/central Europe, the United Kingdom, mountainous areas in France, Italy and northern Spain.

In addition, while there is no significant difference in SOC stock loss between the two considered SSP scenarios for EU considered as a whole (Table 9 and Figure 9a,b), higher losses occur by places in northern and eastern Europe, as well as in the UK and Austria, but also in part of Poland and Massif Central in France (Figure 9c) for SSP5-8.5 compare to SSP1-2.6. This change is entirely due to the variations in precipitation and temperature between the two climate scenarios, since the change in land use is not SSPs dependent in our simulations.

Table 9. Descriptive statistics of SOC stock loss between 1980 and 2050 over the whole soil profile or for 1-metre depth when the soil is deeper under different climate change scenarios (SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5)

	Unit	SSP	Mean	Median	Min	Max	CV	SD
SOC stock to 1 m loss	%	1-2.6	-4.96	-5.02	-35.01	191.61	-1.59	7.90
		5-8.5	-5.92	-5.93	-35.40	192.89	-1.39	8.20

Figure 9. Relative changes (%) in SOC stock between 1980 and 2050 over the whole soil depth or over 1 m for deeper soils considering land use and climate change with two contrasted scenarios SSP1-2.6 (a) and SSP 5-8.5 (b). Areas where the SOC stock loss is at least 10% higher under SSP 5-8.5 compared to SSP1-2.6, in red on the map (c)

2.2.3. Sheet and rill erosion by water by 2050

2.2.3.1. Prediction of sheet and rill erosion by the RUSLE equation: sensitivity analysis and validation

The RUSLE equation factor that has the greatest impact on soil erosion projections is LS factor, indicating that topography has the most substantial impact on soil loss simulation (Figure 10). However, this factor is kept constant in 2050, therefore it will not explain the differences that can be

recorded among the different scenarios for 2050 projections. The model is also very sensitive to the C and R factors, indicating their significant contributions to soil loss, with the C factor showing the potential that vegetation in a given land use has to reduce soil losses and R the effect of rain. Since we only use a land use scenario for 2050, only R will contribute to the differences that may be observed between the two considered scenarios. The K and P factors were less important in predicting soil losses. The impact of the changes in K factors, due to change in SOC content by 2050, should thus be less important than that of the change in rainfall (R factors).

Figure 10. Sensitivity analysis of RUSLE equation to the various factors for sheet and rill erosion by water assessment by 2050 under SSP1-2.6 climate change scenario

For validation concern, we compared the map of soil sheet and rill erosion by water predicted for the current condition to that based on measurements at the EU scale proposed by Cerdan et al. (2010). Globally, the median value for EU of soil loss by water proposed by the two approaches can be considered as not significant ($< 1 \text{ t ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ Table 10).

Table 10. Descriptive statistics of sheet and rill erosion by water ($\text{t ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) from SERENA and measurements made by Cerdan et al. (2010)

Soil erosion ($\text{t ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$)	Mean	Median	Min	Max
SERENA	0.99	0.30	0.00	217.82
Cerdan et al. (2010)	1.34	0.21	0.00	630.21

To compare the two maps, we calculated for each pixel the difference in classes of the SERENA (Figure 11a) and Cerdan et al. (2010) (Figure 11b). About 61% of the EU territory was in the same soil erosion class in the two maps (0 values of the legend of Figure 11c). 17% of the EU territory was either slightly overestimated (difference class 1) or underestimated (difference class -1) by the Serena map compared to the Cerdan et al. (2010). We can thus consider that the SERENA estimation of sheet and rill erosion by water was acceptable for 78% of the EU territory (difference classes -1, 0 and 1, Figure 11c). However, the SERENA erosion map underestimated strongly water erosion for 12% of the EU, notably in the north of France, some areas of Spain and central Europe, and overestimate soil losses in around 10% in the EU, notably in south and north of Spain and Portugal, west of UK, Greece and in the mountainous regions of Italy and Austria (Figure 11c).

Figure 11. Assessment of sheet and rill erosion by water ($t\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$) for present by RUSLE in SERENA (A) and using measurement by Cerdan et al. (2010) (B). Map C represents the difference in number of soil loss intensity classes between the two maps A and B. -1 to -4 express an underestimation of soil loss by SERENA from 1 to 4 erosion intensity classes, 0, no difference between the two maps in terms of erosion intensity classes, and 1 to 4, an overestimation of soil loss by SERENA from 1 to 4 erosion intensity class.

2.2.3.2. Effect of scenarios for 2050 on sheet and rill erosion by water

The potential soil erosion by 2050 is lower than $1\ t\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$ on average for Europe as a whole whatever the SSP considered (Table 11), that is, it can be considered as a negligible soil loss (EEA, 2023; Panagos

et al., 2020). This corresponds to 77.71% and 78.94% of the EU area, for scenarios SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5 respectively.

Table 11. Descriptive statistics of sheet and rill erosion by water projection under different climate change scenarios (SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5) by 2050

ST	Unit	SSP	Mean	Median	Min	Max	CV	SD
Soil erosion	t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹	1-2.6	0.88	0.28	0.00	174.16	2.19	1.93
		5-8.5	0.82	0.26	0.00	142.11	2.16	1.76

However, around 21% of the territory will potentially face notable soil loss by 2050 whatever the scenario considered, with nearly 3% experiencing moderate to severe soil loss, notably in western UK, Brittany and south-west in France, southern Spain and northern Portugal, central Italy and Sicily, Greece, and northern Romania (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Classes of sheet and rill erosion by water (t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) projection for 2050 considering land use and climate change under SSP1-2.6 (a) and SSP5-8.5 (b)

In addition, the mean potential soil erosion for Europe as a whole by 2050 for the different SSPs does only differ by 0.06 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, which was not considered as significant (Table 11 and Figure 13a).

Figure 13. Differences in sheet and rill erosion by water ($t\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$) between SSP1-2.6 and SSP 5-8.5 (a) and areas where soil erosion is at least 10% higher under SSP 5-8.5 compared to SSP1-2.6 (highlighted in orange on the map) (b)

2.2.4. Projection of soil sealing by 2050

2.2.4.1. Changes in soil sealing by 2050

Considering soil sealing changes between 2012 and 2050, we find that in 0.59% of EU, soils will be significantly more sealed. Areas that will experience an increase in sealing are generally located around cities, and mainly in France, especially in the Paris region, and in northern Italy (Figure 14). Considering the area of each country and the area with a projected increase in soil sealing for 2050, Malta leads with a 10% increase in soil sealing, followed by the Netherlands (3.75%), Germany (1.78%), Italy (1.38%), Belgium (1.32%) and Luxembourg (1.28%). The increase in sealing for all countries is listed in the Table 12.

Table 12. Proportion of increase in soil sealing by country (%)

Country	Sealing (%)
Malta	10.03
Netherlands	3.76
Germany	1.78
Italy	1.38
Belgium	1.33
Luxembourg	1.28
Spain	0.80
Portugal	0.79
France	0.72
Czechia	0.69
United Kingdom	0.59

Slovenia	0.50
Slovakia	0.34
Croatia	0.33
Croatia	0.33
Denmark	0.30
Poland	0.29
Sweden	0.13
Bulgaria	0.11
Greece	0.11
Hungary	0.08
Ireland	0.07
Finland	0.06
Romania	0.05
Latvia	0.03

Figure 14. Soil sealing by 2050: classes of soil sealing change between 2012 and 2050.

3. Soil threat bundles by 2050, assessment and mapping

3.1. Methods of bundle analysis

To compute ST bundles, we applied an unsupervised classification on the class values of the four STs that could co-occur to objectively cluster locations (i.e. 1 km² cells) according to their similarity in their multi-STs assessment.

Since ST assessments were categorized into classes and are then categorical data, to compute the bundles, we ran a k-means algorithm on the principal component of a Multivariate Correspondence Analysis (MCA). This last technique transforms the original categorical variables into a set of continuous coordinates in a new space, allowing then to analyze the pattern of relationship of the categorical dependent variables (Salkind, 2007). The number of dimensions chosen for further analysis was made based on the eigenvalue contribution, which suggests that 61% of the total variance could be explained by 5 dimensions.

The k-means algorithm performs a non-overlapping partition of the space into k clusters and assigns each observation to the nearest centre. This allows maximizing the variance between clusters and, simultaneously, minimizing the variance within each cluster. Euclidean distance was chosen as a metric to calculate the variance and guide the clustering process (Xu et al., 2021).

The main question of an unsupervised classification is the selection of the optimal number of clusters. The *NbClust* function of *Nbclust* R package was employed to determine this number by leveraging a comprehensive set of 20 indices (Charrad et al., 2014). This approach provides a robust tool for guiding the determination of the most suitable number of clusters proposed by all indices, the decision being made according to the majority rule.

We use the *Kmeans_rccp* function from the *ClusterR* package (Mouselimis et al., 2020). The initialization step of the clustering process was run 10 times by setting *num_init* of the *Kmeans_rccp* function. The resulting clusters represent ST bundles within the study area.

To support the ST bundles interpretation, a heatmap was generated to visualize the intensity of the different STs for each identified bundle. This visualization allows for the identification of variations in the composition of STs within specific clusters, helping in the interpretation of bundle characteristics. In the heatmaps (Figure 15 and Figure 16), the colors and the numbers represent the percentage of pixels in the bundle belonging to each ST classes presented in Section 2.1.4. An expert knowledge assessment of the heatmap allows classifying the ST bundles into groups.

The final ST bundles map was plotted using the *tmap* R package (Tennekes, 2018) at a resolution of 1km x 1km.

3.2. Results: Soil threat bundles by 2050 under the effects of land use and climate change scenarios

3.2.1. Soil threat bundles at the European scale, number and meaning

The optimal number of clusters determined in the partitioning by 6 of the 20 indices selected in the *Nbclust* procedure was 20 for the two climate scenarios (SSPs), i.e. 20 bundles for the four STs (SOC loss, erosion, sealing and compaction) for Europe.

For SSP1-2.6, five groups of bundles are detected (Figure 15):

- 1- a first group, that represents about 42.5% of the EU, is composed by bundles 4, 8 and 5, in which soils are not projected to be under the selected threats in 2050 (Figure 17).

- 2- a second group, that represents about 34% of EU, is composed of 9 bundles (10, 14, 3, 6, 2, 7, 12, 9, 18, 13) that present only one ST with significant intensity: increase in soil sealing for bundle 10, SOC loss for bundle 13, moderate soil compaction for bundles 6, 2, 9 and 18, and soil erosion for bundles 14, 3, 7 and 12, with differences in the intensity of erosion. The last two bundles exhibit the highest intensity of soil erosion but represent less than 1% of EU (Figure 17).
- 3- a third group, that represents about 22% of EU, is composed of 5 bundles (17, 1, 11, 15 and 20), with two STs with significant intensity: bundles 1 and 11, representing 16% of the EU territory, experiencing both SOC loss and soil compaction, bundle 11 having the greatest intensity of soil compaction; bundles 17 and 20 experiencing soil compaction and very slight to slight soil erosion; and bundle 20 experiencing SOC loss and slight soil erosion.
- 4- a fourth group, that represents less than 1% of EU, is composed of two bundles (19 and 16) with three STs with significant intensity, bundle 19 experiencing increasing in soil sealing, soil compaction and SOC loss, and the bundle 16 experiencing soil erosion, soil compaction and SOC loss (Figure 17).

Figure 15. Description of the 20 reclassified ST bundles obtained for SSP1-2.6: for each ST the percentage of pixels in the different intensity classes defined in section 2 is reported

For SSP5-8.5 scenarios (Figure 16), we also identified groups of bundles with soil experiencing zero, one, two or three STs with significant intensity. The most remarkable change is observed in relation to the transformation from two bundles with two STs to two bundles with three STs. Since bundle 15 in scenario SSP1-2.6 experiences soil erosion and SOC loss, while it also experiences soil compaction in scenario SSP 5-8.5 (where it corresponds to bundle 8). Bundle 20 in scenario SSP1-2.6, experiencing soil erosion and soil compaction, also experiences SOC loss in scenario SSP 5-8.5 (where it corresponds to bundle 19). Changes can also be noted in the southern part of Sweden and Finland where compaction intensity increases compared to SSP1-2.6 (Figure 17 and Figure 18).

Figure 16. Description of the 20 ST bundles obtained for SSP5-8.5: for each ST the percentage of pixels in the different intensity classes defined in section 2 is reported

Figure 17. ST bundles map by 2050 under land use and under SSP1-2.6 climate changes scenarios with the respective area coverage of bundles in the EU territory on the right-hand side

Figure 18. ST bundles map by 2050 under land use and under SSP5-8.5 climate changes scenarios with the respective area coverage of bundles in the EU territory on the right-hand side

3.2.2. Qualitative assessment of the potential drivers of the spatial distribution of the ST bundles

To understand the ST bundles spatial distribution, we visually compared the obtained map of the identified ST bundles to those of potential drivers, such as the mean annual temperature changes between 1970-2000 and 2050, land use by 2050 and land use changes between 2012 and 2050, total annual precipitation changes between 1970-2000 and 2050 and main soil types according to the WRB classification (Figure 19).

The bundles with soils experiencing two soil threats by 2050 (orange and yellow on map Figure 19F), that is mainly soils in southern Finland and Sweden, and Baltic countries (Lithuania, Estonia and Latvia), in Denmark and England, appear to be determined by changes in climate mainly, with a relatively severe decrease in precipitation for England and southern Sweden (Figure 19D); a relatively pronounced change in temperature compared to other northern countries, in southern Finland (Figure 19) and both in the Baltic countries. In the remaining part of Sweden and Finland, where the annual precipitation will increase, the soils are not projected to be under threats by 2050 (Figure 19F). On the opposite, the more severe annual precipitation reduction projected for southwestern France, south of Portugal and south-west of Spain, or the most severe increased in temperature observed for Romania, Hungary and Slovakia, do not seem to increase soil threats (Figure 19D to F).

In southern and southeastern countries, such as Spain, Portugal, France, Romania, and northern Italy, as well as in central European countries and the UK, the projection of ST bundles appears to be strongly influenced by land use with forest and natural areas will mainly experience SOC loss by 2050, while some agricultural areas (e.g. in southern Spain or central Romania) (Figure 19B and F), corresponds to bundles of ST with soil erosion as the only ST.

The impact of the soil type as a driver of the STs is less obvious, this might be due to the fact that (i) the soil types are already closely linked to climate and land use and some effect of soil was attributed to the two other pedological factors; (ii) the STs are here considered as process and as a consequences only relative change are considered. Analyzing the impact of the drivers with a more quantitative approach might elucidate this point.

Figure 19. Potential drivers of the spatial distribution of ST bundles: dominant soil types according to the WRB classification (a); LUISA projected land use by 2050 (b); land use change between 2012 and 2050 (LUISA data) (c); total annual precipitation changes (d) mean annual temperature changes between 1970–2000 and 2050 predicted by ACCESS-CM2 and HadGEM3-GC31-LL global climate models for SPP5-8.5(e) and ST bundles map by 2050 under SPP5-8.5 (f)

Further step will thus consist in a quantitative analysis of these relationships to better interpret the behaviour of ST bundles at EU scale. For that, we will apply redundancy analysis (RDA). RDA is a multivariate statistical technique employed to investigate the associations between two sets of variables (Mouchet et al., 2017).

In a last step, we will gather the feedback from stakeholders on the final outputs of our work at both European and national scales to make sure that:

- the individual ST maps at the European scale fit the national knowledge on the threats. This will be taken in charge by WP3 in collaboration with WP5.
- the bundles maps fit the expectations of the European stakeholders on the evaluation of STs for supporting soil sustainable management policies.

4. General conclusions

This report presents the projection at the European scale of individual STs and of ST bundles by 2050 under the influence of land use and two climate change scenarios corresponding to two contrasted Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5). Soil threats considered are SOC loss, soil compaction, sheet and rill erosion by water and soil sealing. Soil threats were considered as processes and thus expressed as a relative change between 1980 (date of soil profiles sampling of most site from WoSIS) and 2050 for compaction and SOC loss and 2012 and 2050 for soil sealing. Sheet and rill erosion by water however was not assessed as a change between two dates but by RUSLE equation considering both global changes (climate, land use) and SOC content changes.

By using a multi-ST approach, we decided to evaluate ST by simple equation, as already mentioned for erosion. Therefore, soil compaction and SOC loss were assessed by 2050 based on a Digital Soil Mapping (DSM) approach combined with a space-for-time substitution approach. To do so a QRF algorithm was used. For SOC loss, only the part of SOC younger than 70 years was used in this assessment. While soil sealing area estimation exists for present, no soil sealing projections exist for 2050. The only available data are for soil artificialization though land uses scenarios projection (urbanization, industrial and infrastructure), that have different degree of soil sealing. We estimated for each of these land use classes the regionalised average degree of soil sealing in 2012. This regionalised average degree of soil sealing was then used in combination with future land use to assess soil sealing by 2050 and then the change in soil sealing between 2012 and 2050. At last, to avoid bias induced using different databases when performing the multi-ST approach, all the STs were assessed using the same data source for a given parameter. This constraint impeded the reuse of existing ST maps from the literature.

We therefore provided for the first time to the best of our knowledge a map of ST bundles under land use change and climate change scenarios (SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5) for 2050. Four major groups of bundles were identified based on STs combinations, ranging from soils not projected to be under threats to soils experiencing up to three STs simultaneously with various intensities.

These results showed that more than two thirds of Europe will experience no STs or only one by 2050. Overall, the impact of the chosen SSPs on the bundles was rather limited and generally lower than the model precision, despite some regional marked changes at more regional scale. SSP5-8.5 scenario increasing bundles with three STs from the number of two to that of five bundles, representing an increase of 4.3% in the EU territory. The maps of ST bundles revealed that area experiencing several threats are mainly located in Baltic countries, south of Finland and Sweden, Denmark, most of England, Spain, Portugal, France, Romania, and northern part of Germany, Poland and Italy, as well as in central European countries and are mainly driven by climate change and land use. The quantification of the importance of the different drivers of the bundles still needs to be done. The apparent contradiction

between 70% of the soils being degraded and more of two thirds of these soils not or only poorly affected by STs in 2050 is due to the fact that STs are defined as processes while “degraded soils” refers to a state.

Further steps will consist in (1) a quantitative analysis of the relationships between the spatial distribution of bundles and that of the potential bundle drivers such as climate change, land use change and soil types; (2) gathering the feedback from stakeholders on the final output of our work both at European and national scales

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